

August 2025

Research Evaluation

The Value of RDA for Policy
White Paper Series

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This report forms part of a [comprehensive white paper](#) examining the value of the Research Data Alliance for policy development and implementation.

1. The Value of RDA for Research Evaluation

The [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](https://www.rd-alliance.org/)¹ organised workshops on 15 and 20 May 2025, to demonstrate the RDA's policy impact and encourage implementation of [RDA recommendations and outputs](https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/)² in different policy contexts. The workshops focused on critical policy areas that form essential research infrastructure including **Research Evaluation** for creating systems that reward responsible research practices.

The workshops featured lightning talks presenting policy statements and 'Adoption Stories' that showcased practical applications of RDA recommendations, followed by Q&A sessions to facilitate participant engagement with the speakers. During the workshops, co-chairs of the RDA [Evaluation of Research Interest Group](https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/evaluation-research-ig/activity/),³ [Françoise Genova](https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/francoise-genova/)⁴ and [Emma Crott](https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/emma-crott/),⁵ provided an overview of the value of the RDA for research evaluation. They presented a policy statement explaining the importance of research evaluation and how the interest group, alongside other relevant RDA groups, contribute to the necessary evolution of research evaluation.

2. What is Research Evaluation?

Research evaluation is the systematic assessment of researchers and their work for various purposes, including grant funding allocation, career advancement and institutional ranking.⁶ Traditionally, research evaluation metrics have relied on journal article publications and citations,⁷ such as citation count (number of times an article is cited), H-index (number of publications and their citation impact) and journal impact factor (citation performance of the journal where research is published).⁸ More modern evaluation approaches combine these traditional bibliometric measures with additional indicators, such as 'altmetrics' that track online engagement with publications (e.g. downloads, shares, mentions) and a researcher's institutional contributions, such as track record of grant funding securement and number of students supervised. There is also growing demand to measure the societal impact of research to demonstrate real-world value beyond academia.

Principally, no single metric is sufficient to effectively evaluate research. Responsible and reliable research evaluation should use multiple metrics together and consider the context in which research is conducted to provide a more complete and fair assessment of researcher contributions. The goal, therefore, is to move beyond quantifying article publications toward understanding the broader value and impact of research. Initiatives for research assessment reform, including [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](https://coara.eu/),⁹

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/evaluation-research-ig/activity/>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/francoise-genova/>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/emma-crott/>

⁶ <https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/current-status/>

⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8712583/>

⁸ <https://university.open.ac.uk/library-research-support/researcher-skills/types-bibliometrics>

⁹ <https://coara.eu/>

[Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#)¹⁰ and the [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#)¹¹ advise using quantitative indicators only within the context of a larger qualitative narrative.

Although a newly emerging policy area, the necessary evolution of research evaluation is gaining significant momentum within the RDA community and beyond. The RDA's diverse, international network of researchers, data professionals, and institutions is uniquely positioned to support this transformation towards reforming evaluation approaches to recognise the full spectrum of modern research outputs, including datasets, software and collaborative contributions, that traditional bibliometrics overlook. As research evaluation evolves beyond publication-focused indices to embrace the breadth of contemporary scholarship, it will become an essential enabler of Open Science by ensuring all valuable research contributions are properly recognised and rewarded.

2.1. Why should you care?

POLICY STATEMENT

The evolution of research evaluation from being mostly bibliometric based is a key enabler of robust, equitable, inclusive and diverse open research practices. As stated in the first Core Commitment of the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#),¹² it is necessary to **'recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research'**. The evolution should be discussed and signed at the local, national and international level.

2.2. Benefits and Consequences

Transforming research evaluation beyond its current limitations delivers benefits spanning individual researchers to global research systems. The transformation requires visionary leadership and international coordination to drive the necessary culture change.

2.2.1. Promoting Open Science

Recognising diverse research contributions beyond traditional journal article publications incentivises and rewards various contributions to Open Science. Such contributions include datasets, software, models, methods, theories, algorithms, protocols, standards definition and maintenance, workflows, exhibition strategies, and policy contributions, as well as teaching excellence, mentoring, peer-review, public engagement activities, creative works, and more.⁹⁹ Currently, researchers who follow Open Science principles often do so at significant personal cost, risking their careers while bearing additional financial and administrative burdens.

2.2.2. Recognising Individual Contributions

Modern research evaluation creates better alignment between evaluation criteria and the actual activities conducted by researchers. Considering disciplinary differences, research types, career stage,⁹⁹ research

¹⁰ <https://sfdora.org/>

¹¹ <https://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>

¹² https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2022/09/2022_07_19_rra_agreement_final.pdf

environment, and available resources reduces bias against certain domains and career stages. This approach acknowledges diverse research roles, skills, and competencies, including those outside academia, as well as contributions to team science.⁹⁹ Together, this comprehensive recognition of individual researcher contributions creates more equitable career advancement opportunities across different research contexts and career paths.

2.2.3. Enhancing Research Quality

Evaluating the full range of research outputs incentivises reproducible, transparent and ethical research practice through combined quantitative and qualitative metrics that prevent ‘gaming’ of traditional measures like citation counts, H-index and impact factors.¹³ It reduces the pressure to publish at the expense of research quality, thereby promoting long-term foundational research and reducing waste from duplicative or low-quality research driven by publication pressure.¹⁴ Modern research evaluation also encourages more innovative and collaborative research produced by team science over individual competition.

2.2.4. Improving Societal Impact

Recognising innovative research that has greater societal impact demonstrates the value of research in offering practical real-world applications and ensures scientific discoveries translate more effectively into evidence-based policies. In addition, rewards for science communication and public engagement increases transparency and accountability, building public trust in research.

2.2.5. Sustaining Research Infrastructures

Modern research evaluation helps demonstrate the value and impact of research infrastructure and services, justifying their continued investment, attracting further support and ensuring their sustainability.¹⁵ The reformation of current research evaluation practices will require investment in tools and platforms that support comprehensive evaluation approaches. An illustrative example is [GraspOS](#),¹⁶ a European-funded project that investigates responsible research assessment approaches and interventions that consider Open Science practices, and builds a federated infrastructure (open dataspace) offering data, indicators, tools, services and guidance to support and enable policy reform for research assessment.

3. RDA's Impact

The RDA community provides a neutral, international platform uniting multidisciplinary voices to participate in the evolution and improvement of research evaluation practices.

3.1. Evaluation of Research Interest Group

The [RDA Evaluation of Research Interest Group](#), endorsed in 2023, facilitates discussion and connects global reform efforts to redefine research evaluation. Its primary goal is to liaise with relevant RDA groups and external initiatives focused on research assessment reform in aim to advocate for the recognition of data and software as an integral part of research evaluation.

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0221212>

¹⁴ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3999612/>

¹⁵ <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-policy-brief-impact>

¹⁶ <https://www.openaire.eu/graspos-project>

3.2. RDA Value for the Evaluation of Research

In its first year, the Interest Group produced a visionary supporting output that describes the '[RDA Value for The Evaluation of Research](#)'.¹⁷ The output reinforces how the RDA's diverse global network of data experts across all research domains uniquely positions it to champion worldwide discussions on research evaluation reform. This includes fostering strong collaborations with members of the [RDA Organisational Assembly](#), primarily the [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\)](#)¹⁸ and the [Global Alliance for Genomics and Health \(GA4GH\)](#),¹⁹ in addition to members of the [RDA Funders Forum](#). The output also outlines how important liaisons are established with international initiatives on research assessment reform, particularly [CoARA](#).

With over 100 groups and 90 endorsed recommendations and outputs, undoubtedly most, if not all, of the RDA community's work is in some way relevant to the evolution of research evaluation. The [RDA Value for The Evaluation of Research](#) output showcases many RDA groups that focus on metrics and criteria, stakeholder representation, and disciplinary data.

“The RDA's reach across the international community, including research organisations and funders, and the diverse profiles of its individual members, can help to facilitate and align a global discussion about research evaluation, drawing on data experts from a range of domains.”

*- Emma Crott
ARDC, Australia*

RDA groups such as the [Data Usage Metrics Working Group](#)²⁰ and [Sharing Rewards and Credit \(SHARC\) Interest Group](#)²¹ recognise and reward contributions to Open Science. Others support a broad range of related data management practices, including the [Active Data Management Plans Interest Group](#)²², [Reproducibility Interest Group](#),²³ [National PID Strategies Interest Group](#),²⁴ [Vocabulary Services Interest Group](#),²⁵ [Sensitive Data Interest Group](#),²⁶ [FAIR Principles for Research Hardware Interest Group](#)²⁷ and the [Virtual Research Environment Interest Group](#).²⁸

The [FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group](#),²⁹ [FAIR for Research Software Working Group](#),³⁰ [RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software Working Group](#)³¹ and the [Software Source Code](#)

¹⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/evaluation-research-ig/outputs/?output=142666>

¹⁸ <https://www.researchsoft.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

²⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-usage-metrics-wg/activity/>

²¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/sharing-rewards-and-credit-sharc-ig/activity/>

²² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/active-data-management-plans/activity/>

²³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/reproducibility-ig/activity/>

²⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-interest-group/activity/>

²⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/vocabulary-services-interest-group/activity/>

²⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/sensitive-data-interest-group/activity/>

²⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-principles-research-hardware/activity/>

²⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/vre-ig/activity/>

²⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-data-maturity-model-wg/activity/>

³⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-research-software-fair4rs-wg/activity/>

³¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-resa-policies-research-organisations-research-software-pro4rs/activity/>

[Interest Group](#)³² consider the inherent connection between data and software. The [Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem Interest Group](#)³³ considers samples and collections as important assets for many research disciplines. Several groups focus specifically on disciplinary data management within Natural Sciences, Engineering and Technology, Agricultural and Veterinary Science, Medical and Health Sciences (including -omics) and Social Sciences.

The [Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation \(AIDV\) Working Group](#)³⁴ and related [CoARA Working Group on Ethics and Research Integrity Policy in Responsible Research Assessment for Data and Artificial Intelligence \(ERIP\)](#)³⁵ examine the ethical, legal, and social challenges of using AI and data visitation technologies. The [Uptake of Digital Research Infrastructure Interest Group](#)³⁶ will consider the uptake of digital research infrastructure, which can play a role in supporting research evaluation. The [Early Career and Engagement Interest Group](#)³⁷ and the [Research Data Policy Interest Group](#) enables inclusion of perspectives of early career individuals and other key stakeholders within the research data ecosystem on the topic of reforming research evaluation.

In addition, several RDA groups focus on education, training and data support which are essential components for reforming research evaluation. These groups include the [Engaging Researchers with Data Interest Group](#),³⁸ [Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group](#),³⁹ [CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries Interest Group](#),⁴⁰ [Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group](#)⁴¹ and the [Libraries for Research Data Interest Group](#).⁴²

3.3. Evolution of Research Evaluation in Practice

Given the RDA's emerging role in reforming research evaluation, the following section showcases work currently underway within the RDA community and beyond that shapes the future of how research impact is assessed and rewarded.

³² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/software-source-code-ig/activity/>

³³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-principles-research-hardware/activity/>

³⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/activity/>

³⁵ <https://coara.eu/working-groups/working-groups/wg-erip/>

³⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/uptake-digital-research-infrastructure-ig/activity/>

³⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/early-career-and-engagement-ig/activity/>

³⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/engaging-researchers-data-ig/activity/>

³⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/codatar-da-research-data-science-schools-low-and-middle-income-countries/activity/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/codatar-da-research-data-science-schools-low-and-middle-income-countries/activity/>

⁴¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/professionalising-data-stewardship-ig/activity/>

⁴² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/libraries-research-data/activity/>

3.3.1. RDA France: A Liaison with CoARA

“The evolution of research evaluation is indispensable to enable Open Science. In the same way that Open Science promotes the open sharing of FAIR data and other research outputs, evaluators must also value and consider these outputs as part of wider research evaluation.”

- Françoise Genova

Strasbourg Astronomical Observatory, France and RDA France

The [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) is a collective of over 800 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, and professional societies committed to reforming research evaluation methods by recognising diverse outputs and emphasising qualitative judgment over bibliometrics. [CoARA National Chapters](#)⁴³ are country-level facilitators that form hubs for coordinating actions and mutual learning among member organisations within specific countries, helping translate CoARA's research assessment reform principles into diverse geographical, regional, institutional, and disciplinary contexts.

Since the evolution of research evaluation is an important topic in France, a liaison was initiated between the regional group, [RDA in France](#), and [French CoARA National Chapter](#).⁴⁴ The French National chapter (CoARA France), supported by numerous French organisations, aims to create an exchange platform for sharing best practices and coordinating research assessment reform efforts among universities, research organisations, funding agencies, and assessment authorities, facilitating collaboration in the French evaluation landscape.

Over the past year, there has been valuable information exchange between the two initiatives to strengthen the liaison. CoARA France actively contributed to RDA discussions on research evaluation through participation in the [2024 RDA France Days](#)⁴⁵ plenary session and the [RDA 23rd Plenary Meeting session](#)⁴⁶ on 'leveraging liaisons', while Françoise Genova presented on the evolution of research evaluation covering both CoARA and RDA contributions at the [ANDOR2024 National Conference on Research Data](#)⁴⁷ in Marseille. In September 2025, the RDA is organising a workshop in collaboration with CoARA for the research community in Asia and Oceania.

The strong liaison established between the RDA and CoARA at the French national level exemplifies how national presence, through [regional groups](#),⁴⁸ can facilitate transformative policy change in areas central to the RDA's mission. This powerful model requires the RDA community to strategically identify high-impact topics with pan-national relevance, actively propose and champion corresponding RDA groups, and ensure RDA regional groups effectively engage directly with key national initiatives to amplify influence and accelerate adoption.

⁴³ <https://coara.eu/working-groups/national-chapters/>

⁴⁴ <https://coara.eu/working-groups/national-chapters/coara-national-chapter-france/>

⁴⁵ <https://rdafrance2024.sciencesconf.org/resource/page/id/1>

⁴⁶ https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/evaluation-research-ig/plenary-participation/?application_id=171820

⁴⁷ <https://andor2024.sciencesconf.org/>

⁴⁸ https://www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=regional-group

“The liaison established between RDA in France and CoARA France provides additional visibility for the RDA. It enables the national and global RDA community to provide input to a strategic national policy evolution which transcends Open Science.”

- *Françoise Genova*
Strasbourg Astronomical Observatory, France and RDA France

3.3.2. SHARC: Rewarding Open Science

“The evolution of research evaluation is important because it impacts on the practice and integrity of research, shapes research careers and forms the basis of public trust in research.”

- *Anne Cambon-Thomsen*
CNRS, Inserm and University of Toulouse, France

The RDA [Sharing Rewards and Credit \(SHARC\) Interest Group](#), endorsed in 2017, developed [Recommendations on Open Science Rewards and Incentives: Guidance for multiple stakeholders in Research](#).⁴⁹ These comprehensive recommendations, also published in the [Data Science Journal](#),⁵⁰ target multiple stakeholders with specific actions. Institutions should provide digital infrastructure, training, and funding for data sharing; funders must establish open access policies with corresponding support; publishers should adopt open peer-review models and provide open access to articles, data, and software; and government policymakers should implement comprehensive Open Science strategies following [UNESCO guidelines](#).⁵¹ Central to these recommendations is the emphasis on integrating sharing activities into research evaluation schemes as an overarching mechanism to transform research culture toward Open Science, requiring collaborative efforts from individual researchers, institutions, funders, policymakers, and publishers throughout the research and innovation system.

Even before its completion, the work leading to the output was used to inspire and influence various national and international initiatives. It was used by the [French National Plan for Open Science](#),⁵² [National Centre for Scientific Research \(CNRS\)](#),⁵³ [National Research Agency](#), and the [High Council for the Evaluation of Research and Higher Education \(Hcéres\)](#),⁵⁴ to modify their evaluation criteria, incorporating part of the SHARC Interest Group’s ongoing work before the final RDA approval. This was done by soliciting presentations of the SHARC work and outputs at various relevant national events and round tables.

Other related outputs of the group include [‘FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles’ Heel of Applying FAIR Principles’](#),⁵⁵ an article that reports on lessons learned about identifying processes required to prepare FAIR

⁴⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/sharing-rewards-and-credit-sharc-ig/outputs/?output=142427>

⁵⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2025-015>

⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>

⁵² <https://www.ouvri.lascience.fr/second-national-plan-for-open-science/>

⁵³ <https://www.cnrs.fr/en>

⁵⁴ <https://www.enqa.eu/membership-database/hceres-high-council-for-the-evaluation-of-research-and-higher-education/>

⁵⁵ <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-032>

implementation in non-data-skilled communities, and the procedures and training that must be deployed and adapted to each practice and level of understanding. The group also produced [Templates for FAIRness evaluation criteria](#)⁵⁶ that show the criteria researchers can follow to demonstrate their FAIR practice, and published insights from an international survey on '[Gaps between Open Science activities and actual recognition systems](#)'.⁵⁷ Based on responses from 230 participants from 37 countries, the survey revealed that, while most organisations have formal Open Science policies, the majority lack specific credit or reward mechanisms for Open Science activities, with researchers identifying Open/FAIR data management and sharing as most deserving of recognition and preferring Open Science indicators in research evaluation processes.

3.3.3. Open Science NL: Open Science Career Evaluation

“The evolution of research evaluation is important because it shapes our understanding of what counts as ‘excellent research’ and influences the priorities, practices, and values of the academic community.”

- Marta Teperek

Open Science NL/ Dutch Research Council (NWO), Netherlands

[Open Science NL \(OSNL\)](#),⁵⁸ the Dutch programme tasked with accelerating the transition to Open Science, has launched a €1.2M initiative that directly tackles lack of institutional recognition and reward as a core barrier to adoption of Open Science practices among researchers. The initiative was motivated by the understanding that Open Science practices will only become widespread when institutions formally recognise and reward them in their hiring and promotion decisions.

Through targeted funding of up to €50K per institution, this investment empowers every Dutch institution in the [National Recognition and Rewards Programme](#)⁵⁹ to embed open science within their hiring and promotion policies for researchers and support staff. A further €150K was awarded to a national coordination project that will work with funded institutions to facilitate knowledge and practice exchange, and policy alignment. All projects are expected to start toward the end of 2025 and will last one year.

By embedding Open Science into career advancement criteria for both researchers and support staff, Open Science NL hopes to create systemic incentives to embrace Open Science practices. Early feedback confirms this as a cost-effective approach to drive institutional policy transformation, with the potential to change how academic careers are rewarded in the Netherlands.

“For Open Science practices to become mainstream, it is essential that they are recognised and rewarded within institutional hiring and promotion policies.”

- Marta Teperek

⁵⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11243918>

⁵⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0315632>

⁵⁸ <https://www.openscience.nl/>

⁵⁹ <https://recognitionrewards.nl/>

4. Conclusions and Future Directions

The RDA is well-positioned to drive the transformation of research evaluation. Its global, cross-disciplinary community and proven track record of developing widely-adopted data infrastructure solutions gives it unrivalled influence in contributing to how modern research is evaluated. The practical examples described above showcase effective models towards reforming research evaluation, each demonstrate different pathways to systematic change and represent replicable frameworks for other regions seeking to modernise their research evaluation systems.

The RDA France-CoARA liaison shows how international frameworks can be translated into national contexts through strategic partnerships. This model proves that cross-initiative collaboration amplifies impact and provides mutual reinforcement for policy evolution. The success of the SHARC Interest Group demonstrates the power of comprehensive, stakeholder-targeted recommendations. Even before formal completion, their work was referred to and influenced major French organisations (CNRS, Hcéres), demonstrating the value of the RDA for driving and fostering research evaluation policy adoption. Finally, OSNL's financial investment shows how strategic funding can engender systemic change by embedding new values into career advancement structures

Together, these cases illustrate that research evaluation transformation requires multiple simultaneous approaches. The convergence of these efforts across different countries suggests a global momentum toward valuing diverse research contributions, with data sharing and Open Science practices increasingly recognised as essential components of research excellence.

The research evaluation landscape is experiencing explosive growth with many new initiatives emerging at a rapid pace. This creates both unprecedented opportunity and strategic complexity. The surge in interest among the research community reflects the reformation of research evaluation as a defining issue of our era – one that touches every researcher, institution, and discipline worldwide while spanning the entire research data lifecycle. This universal relevance also creates a unique adoption challenge for the RDA. As the evolution of research evaluation involves many stakeholders and initiatives, each concerned with different aspects of the transformation, identifying and engaging the right adopters for RDA's recommendations and outputs requires careful and thoughtful coordination across this vast, interconnected ecosystem. Moreover, due to the fast-evolving research evaluation policy landscape, the RDA's recommendations and outputs require continual updates.

The [RDA Evaluation of Research Interest Group](#) will continue to provide contributions to the international landscape, building on the RDA community's diversity, knowledge, and international reach. The group's next steps are to create a registry of relevant initiatives and disciplinary aspects of data and software research outputs. The topic of research evaluation may be discussed at the Funder's Forum meeting at the upcoming [RDA 25th Plenary meeting as part of International Data Week](#)⁶⁰ in October 2025.

⁶⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/call-for-sessions-rda-p25-as-part-of-international-data-week-2025/>

5. Contributors

We extend our appreciation to the editors for their careful review and constructive feedback on this white paper. Most importantly, we recognise the speakers, case study contributors, and workshop participants who generously volunteered their time, expertise, and insights, collectively demonstrating the profound value of the RDA in shaping research policy and practice.

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6. About the RDA

The Research Data Alliance (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the vision that researchers and innovators can openly share and re-use data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society. The RDA's mission is to build the social and technical bridges that enable that vision, accomplished through the creation, adoption and use of the social, organisational, and technical infrastructure needed to reduce barriers to data sharing and exchange.

As of June 2025, the RDA comprises a 15,000+ member-strong community of researchers, data professionals, publishers, funders and policymakers, that collaborate in working groups, interest groups and communities of practice to create recommendations and outputs. [Individual membership](https://www.rd-alliance.org/register/)⁶¹ is free of charge and open to all who share the RDA's Guiding Principles. To get involved at the organisational level, explore our [organisational and affiliate membership options](https://www.rd-alliance.org/membership/organisational-membership/).⁶²

⁶¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/register/>

⁶² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/membership/organisational-membership/>

research data sharing without barriers

rd-alliance.org